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Modelling strategy of IR lamps with integrated reflector used in the manufacturing process of thermoplastic composite tapes

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Context and problem

Thermoplastic impregnation line (IRT SE)

PhD goal: Unidirectional carbon fiber –PAEK prepreg characterisation

1st step → Modelling of IR oven

Infrared Lamp with integrated reflector

- Non homogeneous spatial distribution
- Model
 - Equivalent cylinder
 - Weighted radiosity

Parameter characterization

Inverse analysis

Heating simulation
COMSOL Multiphysics®

Experimental results

Objective function

Infrared heating simulation

Optimisation
COMSOL Multiphysics®
and Matlab®

Optimised temperature profiles

